

Volume Rendering Using View Adapted Stepping Distances

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Abstract

In this paper we present a method for accelerating volume rendering by judicious choice of the sample stepping distance. This distance is taken for convenience to be 1 unit in the standard algorithm, but the algorithm can be accelerated by adapting the distance to the view direction. Advantage can be taken of the fact that samples occur only on cube faces, and realistically the computational cost of the volume rendering algorithm is reduced by 50%, with very little image degradation. This method achieves an excellent balance between the image quality and computation time. The method involves very little extra computation to initiate, and works for arbitrary viewing directions.

1 Introduction

Volume visualisation is the term given to the process of displaying three dimensional data sets in a way that is easily understandable to the viewer. The two main techniques for volume visualisation are surface reconstruction [1, 2, 3, 4] and volume rendering [5, 6, 7]. Whereas surface reconstruction will present a surface which represents some constant value, volume rendering attempts to display the volume as a whole. The two methods can be distinguished by this fact – surface reconstruction presents only a particular value in the data set, and volume rendering attempts to give a view of the *whole* data set.

Volume rendering has been identified as a costly process to compute, and many attempts have been made to accelerate the computation time [8, 9, 10, 11]. These methods employ simple techniques to speed up ray traversal over the volume, or to adaptively reduce the workload in areas where it will not be noticed. This paper looks at these methods in Section 2. In Section 3 the calculations required by the volume rendering process are examined and the process of choosing the sampling distance to reduce the number of calculations is described. In Section 4 the effect this has on computational time and the images this produces is investigated. Section 5 offers conclusions for this method.

2 Background

The main techniques for accelerating volume rendering are adaptive rendering [11, 12], template-based volume viewing [9] and adaptive ray termination [8]. Variations of the fast voxel traversal algorithm [10] are techniques that can be employed by most volume rendering algorithms to ensure efficient ray traversal of the volume data.

The adaptive rendering technique concentrates computation in the vicinity of sharply changing features. It achieves this by computing a very coarse image. Each pixel is treated as the corner of a square which is subdivided if any of the vertices vary from the others by more than some tolerance ϵ . When a square satisfies the condition that the colours of all of the vertices are within a certain tolerance of all others, the remaining pixels within the square are computed using bi-linear interpolation. Thus the process can be regarded as displaying an image which is accurate to a tolerance ϵ . The image is continually refined by reducing ϵ until all pixels have been computed. The adaptive rendering results in the sharp changes being accurately computed first, with details in the large coherent areas of colour being filled in later in the process.

Adaptive termination of the ray takes advantage of the fact that colours and opacities can be composited in a front-to-back manner, and not just the back-to-front manner of the naive implementation of

volume rendering. As more samples are composited along the ray the accumulated opacity approaches 1, and each new sample has a minor effect on the overall colour of the pixel, therefore we can terminate a ray once a certain opacity has been attained. This reduces computation significantly since opacity reaches high values very quickly when a ray passes through slightly opaque data.

The template-based volume viewing method of Yagel and Kaufman calculates a view dependent ray template which is a path of voxels through the volume. This template is moved over an image construction plane in such a way that the volume is sampled uniformly without gaps. The ray template indicates which voxels are to be sampled, and these voxels are sampled without tri-linear interpolation. The gradients at the sample points are calculated simple, using central differences, thus removing costly tri-linear interpolation of normals. The image is formed by projecting and resampling the image construction plane to the desired dimensions.

These methods all avoid some, or remove all of the costly tri-linear sampling process that is carried out along the ray. The relative merits of each method are compared with that of the new stepping distance method introduced in the next section.

3 View Adapted Stepping Distance

The tri-linear sampling carried out during the ray traversal of the volume is very costly. In choosing the sampling distance, most implementations will use a length of one unit for simplicity.

Figure 1 indicates the situation.

Figure 1: Ray passing through cube sampled at even intervals.

The spatial position of the i^{th} sample along the j^{th} ray is given by $p_j(i)$. The value which is sampled at that point is given by $S_{p_j(i)}$ where the sample is calculated by trilinear interpolation from the 8 neighbouring voxels that make up the cube that contains the point $p_j(i)$. The sampled value is usually the interpolation of the value and normal from each of the 8 neighbouring voxels [9] or the interpolation of the opacity and colour components, and normal from each of the 8 neighbouring voxels [7].

In order to calculate the normal of the sample $S_{p_j(i)}$ in Figure 1, the normals at each voxel v_0, \dots, v_7 must be determined using an appropriate method, such as central differences. This involves the calculation of 8 central differences, each of which involves 3 subtractions, 6 voxel look ups (Equation 1) and one normalisation step.

$$\begin{aligned}
 G &= (g_x, g_y, g_z), \\
 g_x &= f(x+1, y, z) - f(x-1, y, z), \\
 g_y &= f(x, y+1, z) - f(x, y-1, z), \\
 g_z &= f(x, y, z+1) - f(x, y, z-1).
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The normalisation step (Equation 2) involves 2 additions, 3 multiplications, 1 square root and 3 divisions.

$$\begin{aligned}
 l &= \sqrt{g_x^2 + g_y^2 + g_z^2} \\
 g'_x &= \frac{g_x}{l} \quad g'_y = \frac{g_y}{l} \quad g'_z = \frac{g_z}{l}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

To calculate the normals at each of the 8 cube vertices requires a total of 16 additions, 24 subtractions, 24 multiplications, 24 divisions, 8 square roots and 48 voxel look ups.

Figure 2: Trilinear interpolation within cube.

If the offsets in the cube for each axis are r_x , r_y and r_z (Figure 2), the values at $p_j(i)$ are calculated using trilinear interpolation as follows :

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_0 &= (v_1 - v_0)r_x + v_0 \\
 t_1 &= (v_3 - v_2)r_x + v_2 \\
 t_2 &= (t_1 - t_0)r_y + t_0 \\
 t_3 &= (v_5 - v_4)r_x + v_4 \\
 t_4 &= (v_7 - v_6)r_x + v_6 \\
 t_5 &= (t_4 - t_3)r_y + t_3 \\
 v_{p_j(i)} &= (t_5 - t_2)r_z + t_2
 \end{aligned}$$

which involves 7 subtractions, 7 additions, and 7 multiplications for each value that must be interpolated and a total of 8 voxel look ups. Furthermore, if a value such as opacity is required, a further classification table look up is necessary. If the value being interpolated is the normal, each v_i is now a triple and the calculations are therefore trebled. Also each step must be normalised, so a further 7 normalisation calculations are required. A summary of the total required computational operations is given in Table 1.

operation	normal	rgb α	value
+	51	28	7
-	45	28	7
÷	45		
×	66	28	7
√	15		
voxel l. u.	48	8	8
table l. u.		32	

Table 1: Calculations required for trilinear sampling process.

As can be seen from the table, normal interpolation is the most expensive operation, particularly with its 15 roots, and 45 division operations. When this is put into context with the operation of the algorithm, it is realised that for a large image (500×500) and a large data set ($256 \times 256 \times 256$) this normal interpolation can be done up to a maximum of 100 million times. (Number of rays \times the maximum ray length). It is this figure that lead to the investigation of ways to reduce the calculation. One immediate solution is to precompute the normals at each of the voxels in a preprocessing step. The problem with this is the extra storage required – for a data set of $256 \times 256 \times 256$ an additional 200MBytes of storage is needed (12 Bytes for a normal per voxel). As a result of the usual problems

of memory size, disk size and swapping it is far better for them to be calculated on the fly. In reality far less normals are computed during image computation since not all voxels contribute to the final image when adaptive termination is used. In an experiment with the CThead data of 7 million voxels, only 2 million voxel normals were computed.

By choosing the stepping distance to be 1 unit, the samples may occur anywhere within the data set, that is to say, there are no means by which the computational cost can be reduced by taking advantage of where sample positions occur. It can be seen that since these samples can occur anywhere within the cube, trilinear interpolation for the values must be used. If the samples were to occur within the face of each cube, then only bilinear interpolation would be required. This reduces the need to know the normals at all 8 neighbouring voxels to just needing to know them at the 4 face neighbouring voxels. The stepping distance can be chosen so this situation occurs by calculating how far along the ray must be travelled to cross between successive cube faces parallel to a particular axis. By starting the ray on that face boundary, it is ensured that by using the correct step distance, each sample will be in a face, and therefore only bilinear interpolation is required.

The stepping distance is calculated by determining which axis the ray travels fastest in – that is for a given length of ray which axis it will travel furthest in. The rays are then adjusted to start in the closest face perpendicular to that axis, and then each sample will occur in a face perpendicular to the axis. Face interpolation functions are used depending upon in which face interpolation has to take place (perpendicular to the x, y or z axis). The ray is adjusted simply by scaling the stepping distance of the *fast voxel traversal* algorithm of Amanatides and Woo [10] so that the quickest axis has a stepping distance of 1 (2 division operations), and the fractional part of the sample point position is altered so that it is zero in the fastest axis, and contains the fractional placement in the other two axes (2 divisions, 2 multiplications, 2 subtractions and 2 additions). The fast voxel traversal algorithm then continues as normal.

The effect this has is two-fold. Firstly it is no longer necessary to calculate the normal from 8 neighbours, but rather from 4, halving the number of central difference calculations. Secondly, bilinear interpolation is used :

$$\begin{aligned} t_0 &= (v_1 - v_0)r_i + v_0 \\ t_1 &= (v_3 - v_2)r_i + v_2 \\ v_{p_j(i)} &= (t_1 - t_0)r_j + t_0 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Bilinear interpolation within cube face.

Where r_i and r_j are the offsets along the two axes (Figure 3). This involves 3 subtractions, 3 additions and 3 multiplication operations for each value that must be interpolated, and a total of 4 voxel look ups. The total computational operations required are summarised in Table 2, with the old values in brackets.

It can be observed that about 50% of the calculation can be saved using this method.

operation	normal	rgb α	value
+	23 (51)	12 (28)	3 (7)
-	21 (45)	12 (28)	3 (7)
\div	21 (45)		
\times	30 (66)	12 (28)	3 (7)
$\sqrt{\quad}$	7 (15)		
voxel l. u.	24 (48)	4 (8)	8
table l. u.		16 (32)	

Table 2: Calculations required for bilinear sampling process.

4 Comparison and Results

The effect this has on computational time was tested by implementing the standard volume rendering algorithm using tri-linear interpolation and then modifying it to calculate the required interval size, therefore allowing bi-linear interpolation to be used. The new algorithm and existing acceleration methods were implemented in C on a 133MHz Dec Alpha, using as much common code as possible to make the comparison valid. The algorithms were tested on various data sets, but in this paper we will concentrate on one popular data set – the UNC Chapel Hill CThead.

Since the new method increases the interval size, a certain amount of time will be saved due to the fact that less samples will be taken along the ray. In order to eliminate this effect the standard algorithm was modified so that it calculated the interval size, and used trilinear interpolation rather than bilinear interpolation (called Jump in tables). Taking this time into account allows the true saving to be revealed. One final point is that the interval size can vary between 1 when the viewing angle is axis aligned, and $\sqrt{3}$ when the viewing angle is at 45° to each axis. Therefore testing is carried out at various angles to give differing interval sizes. The results appear in Tables 3 and 4.

Angle	Standard Ray Termination				Adaptive Termination			
	Standard	Jump	Bilinear	Gain	Standard	Jump	Bilinear	Gain
45,45,45	113.16	69.18	39.10	26.6%	73.18	54.30	40.10	19.4%
0,90,0	111.53	113.78	65.73	41.1%	64.20	65.53	50.50	23.4%
45,0,45	114.46	84.21	47.11	32.4%	73.73	61.93	35.77	35.5%

Table 3: Computation times for Hydrogen data set.

Angle	Standard Ray Termination				Adaptive Termination			
	Standard	Jump	Bilinear	Gain	Standard	Jump	Bilinear	Gain
45,45,45	365.85	276.57	141.71	36.9%	96.88	84.40	54.61	35.3%
0,90,0	401.67	448.60	244.36	39.2%	103.23	112.50	74.18	28.1%
45,0,45	344.49	351.67	183.01	46.9%	98.68	100.98	64.68	34.5%

Table 4: Computation times for CThead data set.

The normal calculations dominate the volume rendering process, and by reducing the number required and simplifying the interpolation process, substantial savings can be obtained as indicated by the tables. In fact the computation time has been reduced by about 30%–40%. This reduction is to be expected since the amount of computation done during normal calculation is reduced by 50% and also

Figure 4: (a) Trilinear interpolation, (b) Increased interval size, (c) Bilinear interpolation.

the fact that normal calculation requires a large proportion of the running time when compared to the constant calculations that are made, such as calculating ray entry and exit points to the volume. The method gives a better gain for the normal ray terminating method because a higher percentage of the computation time is spent calculating normals, for which the method offers a 50% speedup. Examining the image produced shows very little degradation in quality. This is to be expected since the samples are still being taken at evenly spaced intervals and are taken in such a way that all values along a ray are used in the sampling process. There is no difference between images 4(b) and 4(c), since both have the same interval size. There is a difference between images 4(a) and 4(b) which have been produced with an interval size of 1 and 1.732 units respectively. This difference is caused by samples being taken with larger intervals using the same compositing formula:

$$o_i^{out} = (1 - o_i)o_i^{in} + o_i \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n$$

where n is the number of samples, o_i is the opacity at sample i , and o_i^{out} and o_i^{in} are the opacities coming into and going out of i . The interval length does not come into this formula, and therefore in a volume of constant value, n samples with an interval length of m will give the same opacity for n samples with an interval length of 1.

If $m > 1$ the volume sampled with the larger interval size will seem more transparent than the volume traversed with an interval size of 1. This is quite acceptable since the opacity values are a subjective scheme to allow the presentation of the data.

Figure 5 shows the resulting images for the CThead test data set.

Figure 5: (a) Trilinear interpolation, (b) Bilinear interpolation.

The adapted stepping distances method was also compared to the other popular acceleration methods, and popular viewing models. The results for 400×400 pixel images are given in Table 5.

Method	Adaptive Termination	Figure	Time (secs)
Standard	No	6(a)	731.37
Standard	Yes ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	6(b)	190.01
No shading	Yes ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	6(c)	81.09
Template	Yes ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	7(a)	10.10
Bilinear	Yes ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	7(b)	98.25
Jumps	Yes ($\epsilon = 0.1$)		140.93
Bilinear	No		292.64
Jumps	No		503.63
X-ray	N/A	7(c)	97.66
Maximum	N/A	8(a)	99.71
Depthmax	N/A	8(b)	106.23
Sabella	N/A	8(c)	133.61

Table 5: Results of different methods using CThead data.

For the CThead (Figures 6–8 there is no qualitative difference between any of the images using the standard viewing model. From these comparisons it would seem that the bilinear method with adaptive termination is the one that produces the best results quickly for this data set, being over 7 times faster than the method without any optimisations. An animation loop was created for the CThead using the adaptive termination technique, with and without the adjustment of the step size to enable bilinear interpolation. Using the normal method, the animation took 2hrs 6mins 12secs to produce, as opposed to 1hr 16mins 6secs with bilinear interpolation. There is no visual difference between the two which would suggest that the bilinear method can be used where high quality accurate images are required using the least computational time. The template method is by far and away the fastest method – taking only 10 seconds for the test data, but produces a very coarse image. The image is adequate to gain a rough idea of the data and is ideal for quick visualisations, since it shows the main features. The problem with this method is that the time is not scalable, that is, it is constant for all image sizes, unlike the other methods, which are scalable. It was found that a 100×100 image created using the bilinear method, and scaled up took half the time of the template method to compute, and produced a comparable image, the only difference being the fact that the bilinear image was slightly smoother than the template image, and contained less sharp delineations of features which had provided good indicators in the case of the template method.

The x-ray, maximum, and maximum with depth cue methods produce alternative views of the data in reasonably quick times. The maximum and x-ray methods produce similar images in much the same time. When using the maximum method to produce animations, the head looks as if it is swinging from side to side, rather than rotating, due to the fact that images 180° apart are identical. This situation was somewhat improved by using the depth cueing method, and produces a better animation.

Finally the Sabella image of the skull is interesting, but it can only be used to show how the image differs from the standard methods. The image it produces in the case of the CThead serves no real purpose since the method was not intended for use on such data sets.

5 Conclusions

By analysing exactly how many operations are carried out during volume rendering, it has been possible to concentrate on a method that reduces these operations by about 50%. This substantial reduction has been achieved through the use of a variable interval size which is dependent upon viewpoint, and is calculated in order to make each sample fall within a cube face. This allows

bilinear, rather than trilinear, interpolation to be used, with the associated reduction in computational complexity. This saving has been analysed both qualitatively and also through the effect it has on the execution times of the volume rendering process. Since normal calculation is the main burden of volume rendering, a reduction by 50% of the operations required should result in a large reduction in computation time. This method compares well with other acceleration techniques since it gives a similar reduction in time without the large trade off in image quality that other methods suffer. This method involves very little computation to determine the stepping distance, and suffers from no constraints on the viewing direction and view point. Table 5 shows that this method fits in well with the image quality / computational cost trade-off hierarchy, and seems to be the best choice for *good* images in the minimum of time.

Figure 6: (a) Standard method (b) Adaptive Termination (c) No shading.

Figure 7: (a) Template method (b) Bilinear method (c) X-ray method.

Figure 8: (a) Maximum method (b) Maximum with depth cue (c) Sabella's method.

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